

Acknowledgement

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Decarboxylation of Oxamic Acid in Resorcinol and Catechol

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CLARK¹ has made extensive studies on the decarboxylation of oxamic acid in several non-aqueous solvents. Oxamic acid decarboxylates in resorcinol and catechol in a manner similar to that of oxanilic acid². No kinetic data have been reported for the decarboxylation of oxamic acid in these solvents.

Experimental

Reagents: Oxamic acid used was an analytical reagent grade, m.p., 212°. Resorcinol and catechol were BDH analytical reagents. No further purification of these chemicals was done.

Apparatus and technique: The kinetic experiments were conducted in a constant temperature oil-bath ($\pm 0.05^\circ$) by measuring the volume of CO₂ gas evolved at constant pressure. The apparatus and technique are the same as described in our previous articles^{3,4}. 0.1586 g of oxamic acid was taken in about 50g of resorcinol and 50 g. of catechol separately and allowed to decompose in a constant temperature oil-bath. The CO₂ gas was collected at room temperature in a measuring burette filled with water which had been previously saturated with carbon dioxide.

Results and Discussion

The decarboxylation of oxamic acid was studied at seven different temperatures. The log (V_∞ - V_t) vs t, plot resulted in a straight line in all the experiments indicating that the reaction is of first order, where V_∞ is the maximum volume of CO₂ after complete decomposition and V_t is the volume at time t. The rate constants were calculated from the slopes of the graphs and are tabulated in Table 1. The Arrhenius parameters of Eyring equation based upon the data of Table 1 are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 1—FIRST-ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE DECARBOXYLATION OF OXAMIC ACID IN RESORCINOL AND CATECHOL.

Temp °C	No. of data pairs	Av. k ₁ × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹ Resorcinol	Av. k ₁ × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹ Catechol
140	3	2.57 ± 0.01	1.82 ± 0.02
145	4	4.57 ± 0.01	3.31 ± 0.03
150	5	8.71 ± 0.02	6.03 ± 0.01
155	4	15.49 ± 0.01	9.57 ± 0.03
160	3	26.31 ± 0.02	13.38 ± 0.04
165	2	42.66 ± 0.04	28.84 ± 0.05
170	2	75.87 ± 0.05	48.98 ± 0.05

TABLE 2—COMPARISON OF THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS.

Solvents	Resorcinol	Catechol
E _a kcal mole ⁻¹	38.95 ± 0.2	35.97 ± 0.2
log A (sec ⁻¹)	17.05 ± 0.01	15.27 ± 0.02
ΔH [‡] (kcal mole ⁻¹)	38.14 ± 0.3	35.14 ± 0.4
ΔS [‡] (cal mole ⁻¹ deg ⁻¹)	+13.30 ± 0.3	+10.12 ± 0.3
ΔF [‡] (kcal mole ⁻¹)	31.06 ± 0.2	31.62 ± 0.5
k ₁ × 10 ⁴ (sec ⁻¹) at 160°	26.31	13.38

The decarboxylation of oxamic acid is kinetically first order in both the solvents at the run temperatures of this investigation and the reaction is faster in resorcinol than in catechol, like other carboxylic acids²⁻⁵. No such abnormal behaviour has been observed as shown by oxanilic acid² in these solvents. It has been reported earlier that the single hydroxyl group of resorcinol associates with the carbonyl group of the acid while the other hydroxyl group remains isolated. In catechol the acid associates with the two adjacent, hydroxyl groups of catechol. Hence the bulkier intermediate complex in catechol than in

Fig. 1

resorcinol which might be the reason for lower rate and small decrease in entropy of activation. This is a well known fact that oxalic acid and malonic acid associate through hydrogen bonding to some extent, past the dimer stage to form "Supermolecules" composed of three to four single molecules each⁶. It can be assumed that the single molecule of oxamic acid is responsible for the formation of the transition complex whereas for the dicarboxylic acids associated and molecules may be involved. The intermediate complex may be in the form (Fig. 1).

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Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Benzyl Alcohol by Peroxydisulphate Ion

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THE kinetics of oxidation of different alcohols by $S_2O_8^{2-}$ has been studied by previous workers^{1,2}. In the oxidation of benzyl alcohol by $S_2O_8^{2-}$, Bacon and Doggart³ have shown the formation of benzaldehyde, benzoic acid and a resinous product, but the kinetics of this reaction has not been studied so far. A kinetic study of this reaction is presented in this paper.

Experimental

The experimental set up was similar to that adopted in the reaction of phthalic acid and peroxydisulphate ion⁴.

The preliminary experiments have shown that the uncatalysed reaction is very slow, however, Ag^+ catalysed reaction proceeds with measurable velocity at 30° and above.

Results

Stoichiometry: It is found that one mole of $K_2S_2O_8$ reacts with one mole of Benzyl alcohol upto the formation of benzaldehyde, according to the equation

The overall reaction was found to obey first order behaviour at different $[S_2O_8^{2-}]$. However, the first order specific rate was found to decrease with the increase in $[S_2O_8^{2-}]$ at constant μ and constant $[K^+]$. This may be due to trace impurities present in Analar grade of $K_2S_2O_8$.

However, on recrystallising the sample of Analar $K_2S_2O_8$ three times, the rate constant was found to slightly increase with the increase in $[S_2O_8^{2-}]$ which tends to confirm that trace impurities are probably responsible for this behaviour.

It is pertinent to point out that similar behaviour has been observed in α -phenyl ethanol oxidation⁵.

The reaction is first order in $K_2S_2O_8$ and $AgNO_3$ and Zero order in Benzyl alcohol. Further the first order rate constant remains unaffected by changing $[Benzyl\ alcohol]$.

From a study at six different temperatures (from 308 to 328° K) the following energy parameters were obtained.

$$E = 18.05 \text{ K. Cal. mole}^{-1}, A = 5.57 \times 10^8 \text{ sec.}^{-1} \\ \text{and } \Delta S^\ddagger = -20.61 \text{ E.U.}$$

A large negative value of ΔS^\ddagger suggests that the formation of activated complex involves a reaction either between two oppositely charged ions or between an ion and a neutral molecule. The value of E is approximately of the same order as for the oxidation of 2-propanol⁶ in presence of dissolved oxygen. A large value of ΔS^\ddagger has been reported for a number of Ag^+ catalysed oxidation of peroxydisulphate ion⁴⁻⁶.

The effect of ionic strength is of the same type as found in the oxidation of other alcohols⁷. The negative salt effect suggest that the rate determining process may be between two oppositely charged ions. Similarly the specific inhibitory effect of different ions is also in the same order

In the same manner allyl acetate greatly inhibits the reaction which is suggestive of radical mechanism.

Analysis of the products at different times shows that the amount of benzaldehyde found passes through a maximum while the amount of benzoic acid goes on steadily increasing with time. This leads us to conclude that it is a case of consecutive reaction leading